

Impact of International Trade, Remittance, and Tourism on Economic Development in Nepal

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Abstract

Separate studies have been examined the impact of international trade, remittances, and tourism on Nepal's economy; however, no comprehensive study combining these factors has been conducted in previous research. Nonetheless, this study demonstrates the combined impact of the above-mentioned three elements on Nepal's economy. It is based on secondary data which has been collected from the Ministry of Culture, Tourism, and Civil Aviation, Nepal Tourism Statistics, World Bank Indicators, Nepal Rastra Bank, and other online sources. Time series data is used over a period of 25 years, spanning fiscal years 1999/00 to 2023/24.

The research method is a quantitative design, utilizing descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and ANOVA to meet its objectives. The result shows that GDP growth has very strong positive correlation with remittance, tourism receipt and international trade and all these correlations are statistically significant. However, the model explained 98.1% of the variance in GDP growth. This study underlines the synergic role of international trade, remittances, and tourism to enable policymakers to develop efficient economic policies. It calls for the precise economic models to know more about the drivers of growth for Nepal, offering valuable lessons for policymakers as well as stakeholders concerned with sustainable development.

Keywords: *economic growth, international trade, remittance, tourism*